

Underwater Wireless Power Transfer

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Abstract — The feasibility of transferring power over a wide range of distances and orientation offsets has been proven in air for various commercial applications, notably in the electric vehicle industry, by using two loosely-coupled RLC circuits that are tuned to resonate at the same frequency. Key system concepts for resonant wireless power transfer, such as frequency splitting, maximum operating distance, and behavior of the system as it becomes over and under coupled, are well understood theoretically, and demonstrated experimentally. Although prior work on WPT in air is quite extensive and mature, very little research has been conducted on underwater WPT. In particular, no studies have been published describing how basic system concepts vary within a conducting medium such as seawater. In this paper, we report the results of experiments addressing the effects of seawater conductivity on underwater resonant wireless power transfer, compared to the basic system concepts exhibited in air. Results indicate that the losses due to seawater become noticeable for frequencies around 20 kHz, and can be large for frequencies above 50 kHz.

Index Terms — Inductive Power Transmission, Inductive Charging, Circuit Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

The feasibility of transferring power over a wide range of distances and orientation offsets has been proven in air for various commercial applications, notably in the electric vehicle industry, by using two loosely-coupled RLC circuits that are tuned to resonate at the same frequency. Recent studies [1] on wireless power transfer provide an overview of the theory as well as an excellent discussion of the design issues that must be addressed in order to achieve optimal efficiency at “high” power transfer, i.e. tens to thousands of watts. Other studies [2][3] give an excellent introduction to the theory of highly-resonant wireless power transfer (WPT) technology, emphasizing key system concepts such as frequency splitting, ideal operating distance (critical coupling), and the behavior of the system as it becomes over- and under-coupled.

Although prior work on WPT in air is quite extensive and mature, very little research has been conducted on underwater WPT systems. In particular, no studies have been published that investigate how the basic system concepts are changed in a conducting medium such as seawater. To characterize the performance of WPT systems in seawater, the performance of two perfectly aligned coils in RLC resonant circuits were studied, using circuit theory and open-air and underwater experiments with in-house fabricated coils and tuning circuit elements. The results indicate that the losses due to seawater

increase with increases in frequency, becoming significant for frequencies much above 20 kHz.

II. EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT MODEL

The equivalent circuit for resonant wireless power transfer in seawater is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Equivalent circuit model for WPT in seawater.

Two key differences between a comparable circuit model for WPT in air should be noted. First, as studied by Kraichman [4], the conductivity of seawater adds a resistive component, R_{L1}^{sea} , R_{L2}^{sea} , distinct from DC wire resistance, to the impedance of each coil, and causes their inductances to be a function of frequency. Secondly, the mutual inductance has an imaginary component, which also represents a loss. This can be seen from the expression for mutual inductance of two coils in a lossy medium,

$$M = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} N_1 N_2 \oint \oint \frac{e^{-\gamma|\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1|}}{|\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1|} d\mathbf{l}_1 \cdot d\mathbf{l}_2, \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma \approx \sqrt{j\omega\mu_0\sigma} = (1 + j)\beta$, $\beta = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi f \mu_0 \sigma}{2}}$, σ is the conductivity of the medium, N_1 and N_2 are the number of turns in the two coils, and the circuit integrals are over the path of a single turn of each coil. Solving the resulting KVL circuit equations gives the following expressions for the load voltage, V_{R2} and power efficiency, η :

$$\frac{V_{R2}}{V_{in}} = \frac{(j\omega M_{r}^{sea} + R_M^{sea})R_2}{\Delta}, \quad (2)$$

$$\eta = \frac{P_{R2}}{P_{in}} = \frac{R_2 \left| \frac{j\omega M_{r}^{sea} + R_M^{sea}}{\Delta} \right|^2}{\text{Re} \left[\frac{R_2 + R_2^{DC} + R_{L2}^{sea} + j\omega L_2 + \frac{1}{j\omega C_2}}{\Delta} \right]}, \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta = (R_1 + R_1^{DC} + R_{L1}^{res} + j\omega L_1 + \frac{1}{j\omega C_1})(R_2 + R_2^{DC} + R_{L2}^{res} + j\omega L_2 + \frac{1}{j\omega C_2}) - (j\omega M_r^{sea} + R_M^{sea})^2, \quad (4)$$

where $R_M^{sea} = -j\omega M_i^{sea}$. In the circuit model predictions below, Kraichman [4] is used to calculate values for R_{L1}^{sea} and R_{L2}^{sea} , while Equation (1) is used to compute M_r^{sea} and R_M^{sea} as a function of coil separation and frequency. In both calculations, σ was set to 4 S/m.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

An RLC series circuit was fabricated (see Fig. 2) with an adjustable-value capacitor bank to bring the transmit and receive circuits into resonance with one another. Identical 24-turn, cylindrically-wound, waterproofed coils were designed with a radius of 15 cm. Litz wire was utilized throughout both RLC circuits to minimize resistance resulting from the skin effect at high frequencies. The transmitting and receiving coils had inductances of 338 μ H and 333 μ H, respectively. The DC resistances of the coils were both measured to be 0.2 Ω . A 4 Ω , non-inductive resistor bank was used on the receive side as the load. A 1 Ω , non-inductive ballast resistor bank was placed in series with the transmitting circuit in order to prevent uncontrolled resonant conditions (for safety purposes). Both resistors were actively cooled with chilled deionized water at 7 $^{\circ}$ C to ensure the resistors would remain within their operating temperature range. The configuration of the resistor banks are outlined in Fig. 2. A test matrix was developed that specified measurements for each RLC circuit, tuned to resonate in isolation at four distinct frequencies: 20 kHz, 50 kHz, 85 kHz, and 120 kHz. The three lower frequencies are representative of multi-kW wireless charging systems currently in use for electric car battery recharging, while 120 kHz was selected to unambiguously highlight power losses due to seawater. The test matrix specified two series of measurements: 1) varying coil separation, with the frequency fixed at each of the four above tuned frequencies, and 2) sweeping the frequency at selected fixed coil separations. For the latter, eight coil separations were chosen in 7.5cm increments from 7.5 cm to 60cm. These tests were first conducted in open air (Fig. 3) and then repeated in salt water, with conductivity of 4 S/m, contained within a 500 gal tank as illustrated in Fig. 4.

Fig. 2. Circuit diagram for the WPT test setup. Components in shaded boxes were actively cooled with deionized water at 7 $^{\circ}$ C to ensure they would remain within their operating temperature range.

Fig. 3. WPT experimental setup in open air.

Fig. 4. Underwater WPT experimental setup. Both coils were placed in a 500 gal tank filled with salt water.

IV. RESULTS

A. 20kHz Results

The results of the 20 kHz tests are summarized in Figures 5 through 8. Initial comparison of circuit model values compared to experimental measurements showed the former over-predicted the peak efficiency and voltage gain by 10%. In addition, the experimental quantities exhibited an ideal tuning of 19.5 kHz, versus 20 kHz for the model. In order to determine the cause of additional loss in the experiment, the receiving circuit was removed, and the transmitting circuit was run at its natural frequency in isolation to determine the total resistance of the circuit. That is, the RLC circuit exhibits only resistance at its natural frequency, allowing for easy measurement.

In this case, the measured resistance of the circuit for 20 kHz was 1.5 Ω , a value that was 0.3 Ω higher than the model's predictions. We believe the equivalent series resistance (ESR) of the tuning capacitors used in this test had increased with higher frequencies, thereby introducing additional losses. In order to reflect the actual circuit parameters in the experiment,

the additional 0.3Ω was used in the circuit model. In addition, we increased the values of the tuning capacitances by 5%, and the results are shown in the following figures.

Fig. 5. Ratio between load voltage vs source voltage as a function of frequency in open air. Tuned frequency was set at 20kHz. The solid (dashed) curves are the measured (circuit model) values.

Fig. 6. System efficiency as a function of frequency in open air. Tuned frequency was set at 20kHz. The solid (dashed) curves are the measured (circuit model) values.

Figure 5 compares the measured values for the voltage gain as a function of frequency (solid curves with data points) with the circuit model predictions, with the above mentioned adjustments (dashed curves), for the 8 separation values studied in air. Figure 6 shows the corresponding comparison for the power efficiency. Agreement between measurements and the model is very good in both figures, the only exception being the efficiency measurements made around 25 kHz. Here, the phase angle between voltage and current in the transmitting circuit approached 90° , causing large errors when determining the real input power. The voltage gain values exhibit the well-documented transition as separation is increased, with over-coupling and frequency splitting occurring at 7.5 and 15 cm separations, critical coupling near 22.5 cm, and under-coupling for larger separations. As expected, smaller separation distances resulted in higher efficiencies, and for each distance, maximum efficiency was

obtained at the tuned frequency. However, maximum power output, which is proportional to the square of the voltage gain, occurred at the separation distance of 22.5cm, where efficiency was approximately 40%.

Fig. 7. Ratio between load voltage vs source voltage as a function of frequency in salt water. Tuned frequency was set at 20kHz. The solid (dashed) curves are the measured (circuit model) values.

Fig. 8. System efficiency as a function of frequency in salt water. Tuned frequency was set at 20kHz. The solid (dashed) curves are the measured (circuit model) values.

In the next set of experiments, the entire setup was waterproofed and submerged mid-way in a 500 gal tank filled with salt water having a conductivity of 4 S/m (see Fig. 4). Figure 7 compares the measured values for the voltage gain as a function of frequency (solid curves with data points) with the circuit model predictions, with the above mentioned adjustments (dashed curves), for the 8 separation values studied. Figure 8 shows the corresponding comparison for the power transfer efficiency. As with the results in air, the agreement between measurements and the model is very good in both figures. The same divergences in efficiency values near 25 kHz seen in the measurements in air were observed in salt water. However, the measured values for 37.5 cm separation are anomalously high when compared with both the circuit model predictions and the results in air. Table 1

compares the measured values for peak efficiency in air with those in salt water, for each coil separation values. In the experimental results the drop in efficiency due to salt water at 7.5cm of separation distance was approximately 1%. However, at separation distances of 15cm and 22.5cm, the drop in efficiency from air to seawater was between 4-6%. For separation distances beyond the coil diameter, the drop in efficiency from air to seawater remained below 2%.

Table 1. Summary of experimental results for power efficiency, in both in air and salt water with tuned frequency set at 20kHz.

Separation (cm)	In Air (Exp)	In Salt Water (Exp)
7.5	81%	80%
15	69%	63%
22.5	42%	38%
30	20%	19%
37.5	10%	11%
45	4%	3%
52.5	2%	2%

B. 50-120kHz Results

The tests at 20 kHz were repeated at 50, 85, and 120 kHz to investigate the impact of frequency on the performance of the WPT system. Figure 9 shows the measured values of voltage gain in air (a) and in salt water (b) for a tuned resonant frequency of 85 kHz. Once again, the measured resonant frequency, 82.5 kHz, was a few percent below the target frequency, 85 kHz, presumably due to parasitic capacitances within the circuits' inductors. Comparing Figures 9a and 9b, the peak values for the voltage gain occur at the same frequency for each value of separation, but are roughly 40% lower for salt water compared with air, except for the smallest separation values of the 7.5 cm and 15 cm. Table 2 compares the peak measured efficiencies for all four resonant frequencies, in air and in salt water, for several separation values. The decrease in efficiency with higher frequencies for the measurements in air are due to an increasing effective circuit resistance with frequency, ranging from 1.5 Ω at 20 kHz, to 5.7 Ω at 120 kHz. At 50 kHz, the peak efficiencies in salt water are roughly 65% or lower. At 85 kHz, the efficiencies are 25% or lower. Finally, at 120 kHz, the power transfer efficiencies are below 15%.

Fig. 9. Experimental results for voltage gain, both in (a) air, and (b) in salt water, for a resonant frequency of 85kHz.

Table 2. WPT efficiency η (%) in Air (A) and Salt Water (SW) for the four resonant frequencies at representative coil separations.

Frequency (kHz)	20 A	20 SW	50 A	50 SW	85 A	85 SW	120 A	120 SW
7.5cm	81	80	78	65	62	25	32	12
15cm	69	69	65	54	42	19	51	14
22.5cm	42	38	53	44	43	17	30	10
30cm	20	19	37	29	26	12	17	7

V. CONCLUSION

Experiments have been conducted to examine the impact of seawater on resonant inductive power transfer, and the results compared with the predictions of circuit theory. The voltage gain and power efficiency were measured as a function of frequency at regularly spaced intervals in separation for two 24-turn, 15 cm radius coils in air and salt water of conductivity matching that of seawater, 4 S/m. Measurements were made for the coils tuned to resonate in isolation at four frequencies, 20 kHz, 50 kHz, 85 kHz, and 120 kHz, using two series-configured RLC circuits. The well-documented, fundamental system behavior observed for the power transfer in air, namely frequency splitting, critical coupling, and over-/under-coupling were also observed in the salt water, but with a reduction in voltage gain and efficiency that is more pronounced for operation at higher resonant frequencies. Agreement with the predictions of circuit theory was close for the 20 kHz case. Follow on work includes a more careful measurement of the values of coil inductances and tuning capacitances, and the reduction of parasitic resistances.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was funded by NSWC Carderock Div. under the Naval Innovative Science and Engineering (NISE) program.

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